

Efficient Point to Multipoint Transfers Across Datacenters

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Source: <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/overview/datacenters/how-to-choose/> (Jun 14, 2017)

Inter-Datacenter Networks

- Dedicated WAN networks for a single organization
- Connect many datacenters
 - Increased reliability
 - Load balancing
 - Content is usually served by datacenters closest to users
 - Lower RTT to users ⇒ Higher average throughput (TCP)
 - Less hops to users ⇒ Saves WAN bandwidth

Source: C. Hong et al., "Achieving High Utilization with Software-Driven WAN", ACM SIGCOMM 2013

Source: S. Jain et al., "B4: Experience with a Globally-Deployed Software Defined WAN", ACM SIGCOMM 2013

Need data delivery from one point to multiple points

Point to Multipoint (P2MP) Transfers

- An abstraction model
 - Single source
 - Content is located on a source datacenter
 - Receivers are fixed once transfer begins
 - No join/leaves

P2MP Transfers Today

- Usually performed as separate unicast transfers
 - Wastes bandwidth and can increase completion times
- Multicasting
 - Network-driven (e.g. IP Multicast)
 - Locally and gradually built trees far from optimal
 - No load distribution management
 - Complex session management protocols
 - Client-driven (e.g. Overlay Networks)
 - Limited visibility into network status
 - Limited control over routing
- Using Store-and-Forward
 - Storage and bandwidth costs on intermediate datacenters
 - Can lead to excessive delays
 - More engineering work (running agents, chunking, etc.)

Our Solution: DCCast

- Send traffic to all destinations over a **forwarding tree**
 - Saves bandwidth
 - A controller with global view of network status can examine options
 - Selection according to current network load conditions and transfer parameters
- Use **rate-allocation** and **rate-limiting**
 - A *slotted timeline with fixed rates during timeslots*
 - Rate-allocation at controller according to available bandwidth
 - Rate-limiting at end-points
- Main contribution
 - Forwarding tree selection
 - Weight/Cost assignment to edges

DCCast Procedures

- Update()
 - Is executed at the end of every timeslot
 - Dispatches rate-allocations to end-points (i.e., senders) for rate-limiting
- Allocate(R)
 - Is executed upon arrival of a transfer request R
 1. Selects a forwarding tree T for request R
 2. Performs rate-allocation over T

Selection of Forwarding Trees

- Assume a directed inter-datacenter graph G
 - L_e is the total outstanding amount of traffic allocated over any edge e

- Upon arrival of request R with size of V_R , every edge e gets a weight of $W_e = V_R + L_e$
- R 's forwarding tree is obtained by finding a minimum weight Steiner Tree
- Fast heuristics available that often provide results close to optimal

Analysis of DCCast forwarding tree selection

- Any forwarding tree has a cost that is sum of edge weights
 - Using this cost assignment we stay away from
 - Highly loaded edges
 - Large trees
- Implications of this cost assignment
 - Smaller trees for larger requests ($V_R \gg L_e \Rightarrow W_e \approx V_R$)
 - Trees are selected according to edge loads for smaller requests ($V_R \ll L_e \Rightarrow W_e \approx L_e$)

Rate-allocation

- Complex problem: Trade-offs
 - Static policies: FCFS, ALAP (as late as possible)
 - More predictability
 - Dynamic policies: SRPT, Fair Sharing
 - Better mean times (by resolving priority inversion)
- We used FCFS policy
 - Simple, no rate recalculations
 - Guaranteed completion times given no failures
 - Senders send at maximum *available* rate starting next timeslot
- Calculation of available rates across timeslots over trees
 - $A_e(t)$ is the available rate over edge e at time t
 - Maximum rate of tree T at time t is $r_T(t) = \min_{e \in T} (A_e(t))$

Evaluation

- Evaluated Techniques
 - Selection of Forwarding Trees (Random, MINMAX, DCCast)
 - Rate-allocation policy (FCFS and SRPT)
 - DCCast (P2MP) vs. Point-to-Point (P2P-FCFS and P2P-SRPT)
- Performance Metrics
 - Mean TCT
 - Tail TCT
 - Total bandwidth usage
- Traffic Patterns
 - Artificially generated
 - Poisson arrivals
 - Exponential transfer size distribution

Evaluation: Selection of Forwarding Trees

- We considered three approaches
 - Randomly selecting a forwarding tree (Random)
 - Picking the tree with minimal maximum L_e over any edge (MINMAX)
 - Greedy approach
 - Method used in many research work (minimizing maximum utilization)
 - Picking the tree with minimal sum of W_e (DCCast)
- Results
 - Overall bandwidth usage (not shown)
 - Same for all schemes
 - Mean and Tail TCT
 - $\text{DCCast} < \text{MINMAX} < \text{Random}$

Benefits of DCCast cost assignment over MINMAX

- DCCast limits load balancing for improved BW savings
 - MINMAX does not account for number of edges
 - MINMAX does not account for request volume
- DCCast cost assignment makes it easier to find trees
 - Edge decomposable costs

Small Request with volume of 1

Large Request with volume of 10

MINMAX

DCCast

Evaluation: Scheduling Policy

- We proposed use of FCFS for DCCast
 - Simple scheduling and resources guaranteed one scheduled
 - ***But how much will it lose on Mean TCT?***
- SRPT is the best policy for mean times
 - Challenging to implement: Tree eviction and rate recalculation as new requests arrive
 - Starvation of very large transfers
- Results
 - FCFS performs slightly better in Tail times
 - FCFS increases mean times by 50%

Evaluation: Comparison with Point-to-Point (P2P)

- Properties of P2P-SRPT scheme
 - Based on *K-Shortest paths* (for every transfer)
 - Uses *SRPT* policy to achieve best Mean TCT
 - Rates are calculated using Linear Programming
- Results
 - Both Tail times and BW Usage improved by up to 50% using DCCast
 - DCCast better in Mean times when making larger number of copies

Summary

- Many inter-datacenter transfers follow the P2MP abstraction model
 - One object is to be delivered to many destinations
 - Source and destinations known upon arrival of transfers
 - No joins/leaves
- Perform every P2MP transfer jointly using a forwarding tree
 - Achieve bandwidth savings and reduce tail times
- Opportunistically and dynamically select forwarding trees
 - Allowing all available paths to be potentially used
 - The opposite would be pre-calculating and using K-Minimal Trees

Thank you!

Future Work & Discussion

- Improving Mean TCT
 - Multiple trees each connected to a subset of receivers (addressing the slow receiver)
 - Parallel trees to same subsets of receivers (increasing throughput)
 - SRPT with only BW preemption (trees selected upon request arrivals)
 - Combining forwarding trees with store-and-forward
 - Applying batching techniques for bursty arrival patterns (e.g. apply SJF policy to batches)
 - Applying the fair-sharing policy (rather than FCFS)
- Evaluation using real traces of inter-datacenter traffic
 - Choose scheduling policy according to traffic patterns
- Handling failures
 - Proactive approaches (leaving spare capacity, backup trees)
 - Reactive approaches (rescheduling affected transfers, local activation)